

THE ROLE OF CORPORATE GOVERNANCE IN IMPROVING THE MANAGEMENT OF STATE ASSETS IN UZBEKISTAN

Butikov Igor Leonidovich

prof.

Director Research Center of the State Assets
Management Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Nuraliyev Rustam Turgunovich

Head Of The Department Research Center of the State Assets
Management Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8020567>

Abstract: This article discusses the role of the corporate governance system in improving the efficiency of state asset management in Uzbekistan, ways to further improve it and its importance in the development of joint-stock companies and limited liability companies, as well as the positive results of introducing the principles and methods of corporate governance into the activities of these organizations.

Key words: corporate governance, state-owned enterprise, joint-stock company (JSC), limited liability company (LLC).

Over the past decade, both abroad and in Uzbekistan, there has been an increase in public interest in improving the efficiency of the corporate governance system. The reason for this situation is that the problems of corporate governance are closely related to some of the most characteristic phenomena in the world economy today. These include: the growing role of the private sector in the economy; the strengthening of the trend of globalization and the expansion of the world economy; new conditions of competition for enterprises and management of state assets.

This problem is relevant in the context of a deep and large-scale transformation in the economy of Uzbekistan, caused both by scientific and technological progress, and its systemic and structural transformations carried out in the process of forming a market environment and developing a mixed economy.

The problems of corporate relations are currently one of the most relevant areas of modern economic research. Corporate governance is the most important institution of the modern economy. In industrialized countries, it is an integral attribute of the power system.

The structure of corporate governance in enterprises should ensure:

- protecting the rights of shareholders;
- equal treatment of shareholders;

- recognition of the rights of interested parties provided for by law;
- timely and accurate disclosure of information on all material issues relating to enterprises;
- effective control over the administration by the supervisory board, as well as the accountability of the board to the shareholders.

In independent Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to ensuring the rights and freedoms of citizens, democratizing the state structure, deepening market reforms, creating the necessary guarantees in protecting private property, entrepreneurship, small and medium-sized businesses. Work in this direction continues consistently¹

The implementation of the Program for Reform, Structural Transformation and Diversification of the Economy for 2017-2022 ensured reliable protection of the interests of private entrepreneurship and small businesses, increased the role of private property and ensured a progressive reduction in the presence of the state in the economy.

As a result of denationalization and privatization, more than 600 joint-stock companies have been created and are currently operating in Uzbekistan. As official statistics show, as of the end of 2022, the number of joint-stock companies with a state share was 234 units.

Joint-stock companies in the republic are represented mainly by large industrial enterprises. The key players in this market include Uzbekneftegaz JSC, Almalyk and Navoi Mining and Metallurgical Plants JSC, Uzbekugol JSC, Uzkiymosanoat JSC, Uzavtosanoat JSC and a number of other industrial giants.

According to official statistics, limited liability companies are also developing in the country. As of the end of 2022, the number of registered limited liability companies reached more than 230 thousand units, of which more than 1,200 were state-owned.

In the current economic conditions of our country, the most acceptable and justifying option is such a form of ownership, when the owners of shares become, along with domestic and foreign investors. Over 14,000 such enterprises, created with the participation of foreign capital, already operate in Uzbekistan. There are examples of successful operation of enterprises based entirely on foreign capital and foreign corporate governance methods.

¹ Radjabov F. Implementation of modern methods of corporate governance is the call of the times. May 26, 2016. [Electronic resource]. □ URL: <https://podrobno.uz/cat/economic/fakhritdin-radzhabov-vnedrenie-sovremennykh-metodov-korporativnogo-upravleniya-velenie-vremeni>

Studying the issues of corporate governance, we can conclude that the role of the state as a participant in the management of enterprises is important. It is as follows:

- ☒ the state invests in certain sectors of the economy or certain regions in order to develop them;
- ☒ the state provides control over the functioning of strategic sectors of the economy;
- ☒ The state creates sources of income to replenish the state budget and creates jobs.

Also, the goals of the state, as a shareholder, are much more complex and complex in comparison with the goals and objectives of private owners. The state may be guided by different goals that are not related to the financial results of the company²

Any joint stock company, including those with state participation in capital, has a developed network of corporate relations. The main participants in corporate relations are entities related to the operation of the company, influencing its activities or dependent on it, in one form or another. First of all, these are the management bodies of the joint-stock company, shareholders, personnel, including management. Each participant in corporate relations is the bearer of certain interests and strives to realize them.³

The entry of Uzbekistan on the path of innovative development has posed a number of problems for enterprises in the real sector of the economy, the main of which are the development of modern organizational and legal forms of management, the reform of the production management system and the introduction of methods and management tools common in world practice that allow maximizing their profits, introducing the latest achievements science and technology, as well as smooth out the causes of conflicts of all participants in the enterprise.

Broad prospects for the successful solution of these tasks are opened by the corporate governance system, which allows integrating the efforts of the highest and executive management bodies in the development of a balanced strategy for the development of production, the development of new products and the introduction of progressive forms of management. Therefore, in the

² . Kochetygova Yu.V. Expansion of State Companies: Corporate Governance and Economic Efficiency. Standard and Poors, 09/03/2007.

³ . Kharchilava Kh.P. Bottaev A.Yu. Corporate governance in companies with state participation. // CONTROL. - No. 1(15) / 2017. C. 88-92.

Strategy for Management and Reform of Enterprises with State Participation for 2021-2025⁴ among the priority areas of state asset management, the need to ensure the full transition of enterprises with state participation to market conditions, the full introduction of modern corporate governance methods into their activities was noted.

In conclusion, it can be noted that the measures taken in the past five years by the government of Uzbekistan in this direction have created an opportunity for the development of a corporate governance system, which, in turn, has made it possible to significantly improve the efficiency of state asset management.

References:

1. Radjabov F. Implementation of modern methods of corporate governance is the call of the times. May 26, 2016. [Electronic resource]. ☐ URL: <https://podrobno.uz/cat/economic/fakhritdin-radzhabov-vnedrenie-sovremennykh-metodov-korporativnogo-upravleniya-velenie-vremeni>
2. Kochetygova Yu.V. Expansion of State Companies: Corporate Governance and Economic Efficiency. Standard and Poors, 09/03/2007.
3. Kharchilava Kh.P. Bottaev A.Yu. Corporate governance in companies with state participation. // CONTROL. - No. 1(15) / 2017. C. 88-92.
4. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 29, 2021 No. 166 ☐On approval of the strategy for managing and reforming enterprises with state participation for 2021-2025☐. / National database of legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan (www.lex.uz).

⁴ Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 29, 2021 No. 166 ☐On approval of the strategy for managing and reforming enterprises with state participation for 2021-2025☐. / National database of legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan (www.lex.uz).

